

Article Reference	Origin	Title	Author	Country	Continent	Journal	Year	Abstract	url	Status	Downloaded	Situacao Leitura	Quality Checklist score	Quality Checklist Result	Document Type	# Pages	Selection Criteria	note
49	ACM	Data quality assessment	Pipino, Leo L. and Lee, Yang W. and Wang, Richard Y.	USA	North America	Commun. ACM	2002	How good is a company's data quality? Answering this question requires usable data quality metrics. Currently, most data quality measures are developed on an ad hoc basis to solve specific...	https://doi.org/10.1145/505248.506010	Accepted	Sim	Finalizado	7	Extraível	Article	8	Focus on Measures and Indicators	
50	ACM	What Are the Most Important Factors for Accounting Information Quality and Their Impact on the Trust in Open Government Data: A Quantitative Study about the Effects of Data Quality on Trust in Open Government Data	Xu, Hongjiang	USA	North America	ACM Journal of Data and Information Quality	2015	The accounting information system (AIS) is one of the most critical systems in any organization. Data quality plays a critical role in a data-intensive, knowledge-based economy. The previous research assumes that poor quality of Open Government Data (OGD), OGD portals, and the services provided for OGD result in reduced trust of citizens in OGD. Data quality is a central issue for many information-oriented organizations. Recent advances in the data quality field reflect the view that a database is the crux of a manufacturer. Data quality issues such as missing, erroneous, extreme and outlier values undermine analysis and are time-consuming to find and fix. Automated methods can help identify anomalies. Data Quality (DQ) has gained popularity in recent years due to the increasing reliance on data in machine learning (ML). The DQ domain itself can benefit from ML, which is able to learn. One of the major drawbacks of federated learning (FL) is data imbalance and uneven reliability of clients, which adversely impacts model performance and generalization ability. Among in data analysis, a significant amount of erroneous or incomplete data can render informed organizational decisions prompting the need for automated data cleaning. Leverano successful! The energy system in Germany consists of a large number of distributed facilities, including millions of PV plants, wind turbines, and biomass plants. To understand and measure this in the modern era, the avenues for data generation have significantly evolved, and therefore, large-scale and diverse troves of data are being collected for downstream tasks. Data quality is critical to make data-driven business decisions reliable, accurate, and complete. As a result, data quality assessment has become a prevalent topic among researchers. Cooperative information systems (CIS) are often characterized by a high degree of data replication; as an example, in an e-government scenario, the personal data of citizens are stored in this time the big data became an important part of all areas, it can be used to improve industrial, banking, education, information, networks, energy, health care, etc. So, because building and integrating industrial information, education, information, networks (IIM) methodology workflow serve as complementary data repositories, and are capable of storing Open government data has become an important movement for government administrations in numerous countries. Previous studies have paid less attention to the complex relationship between government data (GD) is an assortment of datasets designed by government to share a portal with the goal of promoting the legitimacy and openness of government. Human activity prediction (HAP) has gained attention as a significant technology that can enhance the quality of human life. However, existing HAP works have not taken great challenges. Big Data (BD) has already reached a plateau of productivity in a variety of business areas. Meanwhile, the rise of ID to solve economic development promoted by public administration is. This survey paper delves into the sophisticated applications of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques in the realm of depression detection. By leveraging a variety of Big data's explosive growth has transformed several businesses by making it possible to glean insightful information from big, complex databases. This study examines new developments in Particulate matter is an important aspect of air quality monitoring as it directly affects human health. Commonly, sampling stations from satellites are used for broad coverage of aerosol levels. An application in a health care setting is identifying anomalies. This study discusses one such novelty in the use of machine learning and IoT for the prediction of river-local AQI. The digitization of the energy industry enables the collection and analysis of vast amounts of consumption data for improved decision-making and efficient energy resource utilization. This Collecting relevant and clean insightful data is integral to the development of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) prediction models. Most of the current SV datasets rely on SV-finance. The optimism about the benefits of using artificial intelligence to innovate public services is tempered by concerns about its risks, limitations, and dilemmas. Given the rapid changes in the Data quality is critical in supporting accurate decision-making in today's digital era. Key attributes such as data completeness, accuracy, consistency, and relevance must be maintained to Subcontractors' material requires significant interactions with Key Supply Chain Partners (KSCPs) in the construction industry. This article addresses Sharing government data with the public is a government initiative to increase accountability, transparency, and citizen participation. Though open government data (OGD) portal and Computer vision has become indispensable in various applications, including autonomous driving, medical imaging, security and surveillance, robotics, and outdoor navigation. This study examined the barriers that exist in the adoption of AI among various industrial sales processes. Using the Total Interpretive Structural Modeling (TISM) approach, this key investigation explores all the various ways that artificial intelligence (AI) is affecting management techniques. The study highlights the dichotomy between automation and augmentation. Background: As U.S. legislators are urged to combat ghost networks in behavioral health and address the provider data quality issue, it becomes important to better characterize the Data quality details the design and implementation of a Data Governance course using the AGO2 model and the Brightspace platform. The course aimed to develop data management Recent years have seen a significant shift in Artificial Intelligence from model-centric to data-centric approaches, highlighted by the success of large foundational models. The outbreak of viral infections has led to governments and experts worldwide joining forces to find adequate measures and tactics for controlling and eventual community revival. With the Particulate matter (PM) monitoring and data analysis, mitigation actions have been promoted due to the Paris agreement's emphasis on their impact on health and high mortality. This study focuses on heavy metal pollution in Yunnan Province and designed and developed a data informatization platform for soil environmental quality monitoring and data informatization for Sri Lanka is among the 16 countries with the highest leprosy burden in the world. This study aims to explore the relationship between data from Sri Lanka and data quality has not been ascertained. The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a formidable tool in economic predictions is set to change earlier methods with unprecedented possibilities in processing big data sets. While data quality and quantity directly affect the estimation accuracy of deep learning (DL)-based localization techniques, obtaining essential position data is often costly due to time in the healthcare industry, sharing confidential information is indispensable. This is typically done using Electronic Medical Records (EMR). When used along with Blockchain technology, Data governance is social in the government sector, emphasizing data privacy and ethics. The rise of synthetic data in Data-Centric AI has the potential to address data quality. Background: The Ethiopian government, supported by NORAD, the WHO, and other partners, is decentralizing diabetes care to primary health units via a task-shifting approach. Despite This paper uses bibliometric analysis to investigate how data management research has changed over time regarding electronic government or e-government information and This paper presents a comprehensive review of frameworks addressing heterogeneous federated learning, emphasizing the importance of multimodality and fusion techniques in the Recent advancements in deep learning for predicting arterial blood pressure (ABP) have prominently featured shocholotolomochach (PPG) signals. Notably, PPG signals in general, the data collection involves monitoring over the widespread use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and business analytics to use the potential and success of firms fully. In this paper, we have used various algorithms such as Gradient Boost Regression, Catboost Regression, Decision Tree Regression and XGboost Regression by categorizing										

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237	Scopus	Research on Open Government Data Quality Evaluation Index System; 开放政府数据质量评估				Information studies: Theory and Application	2023	(Purpose / significance) The quality problems of open government data hinder the release of data value, which has become both a critical issue and a tough issue in the sustainable Under the background of the current development of science and technology, new technologies have been applied in the development of various industries in the neighborhoods cities, and Public statistical data is a general term for data and analysis reflecting economic and social phenomena collected, collated and used by government statistical departments through various With the acceleration of digital transformation of electric power enterprises, the scale and complexity of data within electric power enterprises are increasing, and data quality and data Massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) is a promising technique to overcome the explosive increase in the demand for high-speed data. quality of service and energy efficiency for fifth The retail industry is undergoing a significant transformation driven by the utilization of big data. This transformative power enables retailers to gain profound insights into consumers.	https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2023.100511	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado	Article	Irrelevant Research Focus					
238	IEEE	Research on Public Administration Decision Model Based on Big Data Association Rules Mining	Guo, Fengji				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado					Cited by 3		
239	IEEE	Research on Public Management Statistical Data Quality Management Based on Fuzzy Clustering	Li, Minghui and Zhu, Xiaoming				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
240	IEEE	Research on the Data Governance in Power Industry Based on Data Owner	Zheng, Yi and Zhang, Ruiqiang and Xu, Jia and Gong, Yan and You, W.			IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology	2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado					Focus on Non-related technical aspect		
241	IEEE	Restricted Search Space Exploration With Refinement for Symbol Detection in Uplink	Datta, Arjit and Majhi, Sudhan				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
242	IEEE	Retail Transformation Through Big Data in Inventory Control and Consumer Analytics	Srivastava, Shikhar and Tripathi, Kausabh Mani and Sharma, Prashant and Singh, Anand and Raj, Arman and Sharma, Vandana and Rani, Seema and Balasany, Anand and Choudhary, Anand				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
243	IEEE	Revealing AI-Based Ed-Tech Tools Using Big Data	Raj, Arman and Sharma, Vandana and Rani, Seema and Balasany, Anand and Choudhary, Anand				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
244	IEEE	Robust Spatial-Temporal Motion Coherent Priors for Multi-View Video Coding Artifact Reduction	Jeon, Gyuhe and Lee, Yeonjin and Lee, Jung-Kyung and Kim, Yong			IEEE Access	2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
245	ACM	SEAAQO 2023: Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Software Engineering and AI for Data Quality (SEAAQO 2023) taking place on December 4, co-located with the ACM Joint					2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado						Short Paper (four pages or less)	
246	IEEE	Social Insurance, Living Standard and Pension Responsibility	Jiamin, He and Hongyan, Li and Xuli, Ji				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
247	IEEE	Software Vulnerability Detection using Large Language Models	Purba, Mounita Das and Ghosh, Arpita and Radford, Benjamin J. and Nijeshbabai, Mahdi M. and Cronenberg, Felipe A.				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
248	Scopus	Systemic effects of an open government program on data quality, the case of the New York State's National Bathymetric Source	Rice, Glen and Wylie, Katrina and Callagher, Barry and Coley, Matthew			Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy	2023		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1080/17513758.2023.2241111	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado	Article	Focus on Non-related technical aspect					
249	IEEE	Theoretical and Practical Aspects of Smart City Data Quality	Rice, Glen and Wylie, Katrina and Callagher, Barry and Coley, Matthew				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado					Cited by 2		
250	IEEE	Theory of Change for the Transformation Towards Open Smart and Sustainable Mobility	Alm, Håkan and Zineb and Sabri, Essaid and Saad, Walid and Nesh-Nash, Tarik				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
251	IEEE	Three-Dimensional Data Security Architecture of Agricultural Supply Chain Driven by Blockchain	Chen, Xiao and Wang, Bingbing and Li, Quling and Zhang, Guofeng and Li, Yuxin and Wang, Yuxin and Wang, Yuxin				2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
252	IEEE	Uncovering the Risks and Drawbacks Associated With the Use of Synthetic Data for Generational	Koo, Seomin and Park, Charjun and Kim, Seobwan and Kim, Seobwan			IEEE Access	2023			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
253	Scopus	Using Synthetic Data for Generational Data Quality Improvement: Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, Maintenance (RE-AIM) Model	Chen, Xiao and Wang, Bingbing and Li, Quling and Zhang, Guofeng and Li, Yuxin and Wang, Yuxin and Wang, Yuxin			Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice	2023		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1016/j.njcp.2023.100000	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado	Article	Irrelevant Research Focus					
254	ACM	Who Broke Amazonian Recharge Turf? An Analysis of Crowdsourcing Data Quality over Time	Marshall, Catherine C. and Goguladine, Partha S.R. and Ghosh, Arpita and Ghosh, Arpita				2023		https://doi.org/10.1145/3578503.3583822	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado						Cited by 0	
255	IEEE	Data Quality Management Improvement: Case Study PT BPI	Sunandar, Nandang and Nizar Hidayanto, Achmad			2022 IEEE World AIoT Congress, AIoT 2022	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/aiot2022.10100000	Accepted	Sim	Finalizado	6	Não extraiável	Conference Paper	6	Relevance to Data Quality or Data Governance	Faz correspondência entre data quality e drink, não há correspondência		
256	Scopus	Data Quality Management Improvement: Case Study PT BPI	Sunandar, Nandang and Nizar Hidayanto, Achmad				2022			Duplicated	Sim		Anda não avaliado					Duplicated Publication		
257	IEEE	Enhanced analysis of Open Government Data: Proposed metrics for improving data quality	Bouchelouche, Khadidja and Ghomri, Abdelassamad Réda and Ghomri, Abdelassamad Réda and Saez, Cesar Garcia				2022			Duplicated	Não		Anda não avaliado					Duplicated Publication		
258	Scopus	Improving open data quality through citizen engagement and data engineering	Saez, Cesar Garcia			ACM International Conference Proceeding	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1145/3578503.3583822	Duplicated	Não		Anda não avaliado							
259	IEEE	Strategy to Improve Data Quality Management: A Case Study of Master Data at Government	Nuhansa, Rizka and Taufiq, Nur Fajar and Rudevinyati, Yova				2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/icc4.2022.10000000	Duplicated	Não		Anda não avaliado						Cited by 0	
260	Scopus	The Importance of Data Quality to Reinforce COVID-19 Vaccination Scheduling System: Study on the Role of Data Quality in the Scheduling System	Siregar, Dwi Yanti and Abbar, Nur Hafid and Hidayanto, Achmad and Hidayanto, Achmad and Hidayanto, Achmad			Proceedings - 2022 2nd International Conference on Information Technology and e-Business (ICITeB 2022) - 6th	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/icc4.2022.10000000	Duplicated	Não		Anda não avaliado						Duplicated Publication	
261	Scopus	The Perspective of Data Quality Rules in Google Forms	Hidayanto, Achmad and Hidayanto, Achmad and Hidayanto, Achmad and Hidayanto, Achmad			International Symposium on Information Technology and e-Business (ICITeB 2022) - 6th	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/icc4.2022.10000000	Duplicated	Não		Anda não avaliado						Cited by 3	
262	Scopus	A Framework for Evaluation and Improvement of Open Government Data Quality: Application to the Case of the National Bathymetric Source	Raca, Vigan and Velinov, Goran and Dzalev, Stefan and Kon-Posovska, Marija and Velinov, Goran and Velinov, Goran				2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/icc4.2022.10000000	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado						Cited by 9	
263	IEEE	An Integrated Hydrophone Calibration System for Ocean Observing: ONO Hydrocal	Billard, Ben and Morgan, Manuel and Mulvaney, David and Dalin, Tom and Mulvaney, David and Dalin, Tom				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
264	IEEE	An Update on the Fully Digital Phased Array Development for Next Generation Weather Radar	Shahper, Matthew and Conway, M. David and Thomas, Henry and Thomas, Henry and Thomas, Henry and Thomas, Henry				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
265	IEEE	Analysis of Design Implementation Guidelines for Data Governance Management Based on DAMA-DMBOL	Hendrawan, Fadhil Rizki and Kusumawati, Ten Fabrianis and Kusumawati, Ten Fabrianis and Kusumawati, Ten Fabrianis				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
266	IEEE	Analytics and Blockchain for Data Integrity in the Pharmaceuticals Industry	Kavasilidis, Iliak and Lallas, Efstathios and Georgianni, Vasilis and Georgianni, Vasilis and Georgianni, Vasilis				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
267	IEEE	Analyzing and Evaluating Critical Cyber Security Challenges Faced by Vendor Organizations in the Pharmaceutical Industry	Khan, Abdul Wahid and Zaki, Shah and Khan, Fahem and Tahir, M. and Tahir, M. and Tahir, M.			IEEE Access	2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
268	IEEE	Application of Machine Learning to Oscillation Detection using PMU Data based on Priority	Mohamed, Tarek and Kezunovic, Mladen and Obradovic, Zoran and Kezunovic, Mladen and Obradovic, Zoran				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
269	IEEE	Assessing Sleep Quality Using Mobile EMA: Opportunities, Practical Consideration, and Challenges in Open Government Data Implementation: A Systematic Literature Review	Lim, Jiyoun and Jeong, Chi'yeon and Lim, Jeong Muk and Chung, Ashraf, S.M. Manjufra and Iqbal, Azman Mat and Anwar, Norizan			IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing	2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
270	IEEE	Comparative Analysis of Techniques for Big-data Performance Testing	Hasanlou, Amir and Vajay, and Dwaker, Chandan				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
271	IEEE	Content-Based Video Retrieval With Prototypes of Deep Features	Yoon, Hyek and Han, J.-Hyung			IEEE Access	2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
272	IEEE	Data Governance Maturity as Initiative for Higher Educational Organization	Kaewkamol, Pornida				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
273	IEEE	Data Governance Maturity Assessment: A Case Study Directorate General of Corrections	Mirza Harawanto, Ikhsan and Nizar Hidayanto, Achmad				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
274	Scopus	Data Quality Applied to Open Databases: COVID-19 Cases and COVID-19 Vaccines	Pasiani, Ariel and Torres, Juan Ignacio and Esponda, Silvia and Esponda, Silvia			Communications in Computer and Information Science	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-63037-3_12	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado	Conference Paper	Irrelevant Research Focus					
275	Scopus	Data quality evaluation in open data in the Rodrigues, Alfonso and Caro, Rodriguez, Alfonso and Caro, Rodriguez	Torres, Alfonso and Caro, Rodriguez and Caro, Rodriguez and Caro, Rodriguez			Ingenieria	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-63037-3_12	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado	Article	Focus on Non-related technical aspect			Cited by 0		
276	ACM	Data quality issues for vibration sensors: a case study in ferrous production	Waszak, Marjyna and Moen, Terje and Ednes, Sjoelvie and Staak, Sjoelvie and Staak, Sjoelvie				2022		https://doi.org/10.1145/3549037.3561273	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado						Irrelevant Research Focus	
277	IEEE	Data Quality Problem in AI-Based Network Intrusion Detection Systems Studies and a Proposed Solution	Halidemi, Maj, Emre and Karacan, Hacer and Pihleas, Muzio and Pihleas, Muzio and Pihleas, Muzio				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
280	ACM	Data Quality, Mismatched Expectations, and Moving Requirements: The Challenges of User-Centric Data Quality Management	Ahmad, Mohammed and Ahmad, Omar and Cincch, Sarah and Cincch, Sarah and Cincch, Sarah				2022		https://doi.org/10.1145/3546155.3546708	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado						Irrelevant Research Focus	
281	IEEE	Development of an environmentally friendly electricity monitoring platform	Li, Changyan and Zhang, Fen and Min, Xn			IEEE Internet Computing	2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
282	IEEE	Elastic Data Analytics for the Cloud-to-Things Continuum	Lato, Sergio and Berrocal, Javier and Ferrández, Pablo and García, Juan and Ferrández, Pablo and García, Juan				2022			Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							
283	Scopus	Enhanced analysis of Open Government Data: Proposed metrics for improving data quality	Bouchelouche, Khadidja and Ghomri, Abdelassamad Réda and Ghomri, Abdelassamad Réda and Saez, Cesar Garcia			ISIA 2022 - International Symposium on Informatics and Applications	2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/isa2022.10000000	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado	Conference Paper	Irrelevant Research Focus				Cited by 2	
284	IEEE	Factors Affecting Information Assurance for Big Data	Utomo, Rio Qutub and Nayha, Farahazillah and Amarnahad, Pradana and Hidayanto, Achmad				2022		https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?url=https://doi.org/10.1109/icc4.2022.10000000	Rejected	Não		Anda não avaliado							

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381	IEEE	Exploring the Influence of Organizational Context on Cross-boundary Information-Sharing Initiatives: The Case of Saudi Arabia (SA)	Ghaurav, Mohammed A. and Aneame, Hashim H.				2020	This study addresses the organizational factors influencing cross-boundary information sharing (CBIS) initiatives within the context of Saudi Arabia (SA). The study starts by synthesizing the significant role of high-quality data in environmental pollution has been in the Chinese central government's concrete efforts to improve its monitoring system, which had digitalization of different industries led by new systems that provide accurate information that results in efficient and effective services. This information is vital for decision-making and on the	https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?...	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	
382	Scopus	Has third-party monitoring improved environmental quality? An analysis of air pollution data in China	Niu, XueJiao and Wang, Xiaohu and Guo, Jie and Wang, XueJian			Journal of Environmental Management	2020	This paper empirically investigates the impact of human capital structure in the process of China's economic transition from a high-speed growth stage to a high-quality development stage. A Data is a collection of facts or information collected from various sources that are used to analyze and interpret the quality of decision-making in an organization. Data cleansing ensures that the data in today's digital world, maintaining the quality of the data is emerging as the keystone of business to obtain high quality data to make sure that the organizations create accurate and vital.	https://www.scopus.com/wardrecord.uri?...	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 46
383	IEEE	Healthcare Management System with Sales Analytics using Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average	Mesrik, Maria Clarice R. and Malaki, Ernesto G. and Ong, Paul Lawrence				2020	The use of uncensored systems within NOAA as a research and operational tool is well-documented. The full benefits of uncensored systems to achieving the NOAA mission have	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
384	IEEE	Human Capital Structure and High-Quality Development: An Empirical Study	Miao, Zhongyuan and Wang, Zhen and Wang, Zhen and Wang, Zhen				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
385	IEEE	Implementation of Data Cleansing Null Method for Data Quality Management Dashboard using Python	Sulisty, Haidar Alwianda and Kusumasan, Tien Fabrianti and Anon, Fikri Muzakkar and Sulisty, Haidar Alwianda and Kusumasan, Tien Fabrianti and Anon, Fikri Muzakkar				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
386	IEEE	Implementation of Data Cleansing Pattern Module for Data Quality Management Application using Python	Sulisty, Haidar Alwianda and Kusumasan, Tien Fabrianti and Anon, Fikri Muzakkar and Sulisty, Haidar Alwianda and Kusumasan, Tien Fabrianti and Anon, Fikri Muzakkar				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
387	IEEE	Implementing an Innovative, Robust, and Emcompassing Uncensored System Data Enterprise	Mesrik, Sharon and Burger, Eugene and Petrakis, Dawn and Hoffman, Paul and Moore, Thomas and McCulloh, Ian and Keenan, Kevin and Kent, Trevor				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
388	IEEE	Improved Estimation of Daily COVID-19 Rate from Incomplete Data	McCulloh, Ian and Keenan, Kevin and Kent, Trevor				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
389	IEEE	Improving Government Decision Making in Africa through Digital Data Collection	Breylenbach, Johan and Hattas, Mathier				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
390	IEEE	Incorporating Discrete Unmanned Maritime System Data Collections into NCEI Synthesized Data	Mesrik, Sharon and Wang, Zhankun and Mahonov, Alway and Boyer, William and Charles and Vardi, Nagura, Charles and Vardi, Mohamed and Mugagga, Malimbo Uch, Emmanuel Sebastian				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
391	Scopus	Nationalized data quality assessments: A critical pathway to improving the accuracy of the data for AI	Liang, Ding and Yan, Banghua and Sun, Ninghai and Fiyam, Lawrence			BMC Health Services Research	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
392	ACM	An assessment of the data quality of algorithmic policing systems	Uch, Emmanuel Sebastian				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
393	IEEE	Lifetime Performance Assessment of SHPP	Liang, Ding and Yan, Banghua and Sun, Ninghai and Fiyam, Lawrence				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
394	IEEE	Open Government Data (OGD) Literature Review	Bahtiar, Arief and Suhada and Muhammad, Wardani				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
395	IEEE	Managing Artificial Intelligence Deployment in the Public Sector	Campion, Averil and Hernandez, Mita-Gasco and Mikhaylov, Jarkim			Computer	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
396	IEEE	Modulation of seismic noise near the San Jacinto fault in southern California: origin and implications	Marynow, Vladislav G and Atiliz, Fernando and Kib, Didi and Vernon, Lance, Veronica P. and Abecassis, Melanie and Soracco, Michael and Hassen, Soumya Ben and Clement, Delphine			Geophysical Journal International	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
397	IEEE	Modulation of seismic noise near the San Jacinto fault in southern California: origin and implications	Marynow, Vladislav G and Atiliz, Fernando and Kib, Didi and Vernon, Lance, Veronica P. and Abecassis, Melanie and Soracco, Michael and Hassen, Soumya Ben and Clement, Delphine			Geophysical Journal International	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
398	Scopus	Open Data Quality Dimensions and Metrics: State of the Art and Applied Use Cases	Hassen, Soumya Ben and Clement, Delphine			Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
399	IEEE	Open Innovation Initiatives to Tackle COVID-19 Crises: Impose Open Innovation and Openness in the Quality Control	Teriz, Serdar and Broo, Didem			IEEE Engineering Management Review	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
400	IEEE	Quality Control Relevance on Acquisition of Large Scale Geospatial Data to Urban Territorial Planning	Filho, A. G. G. and Borba, P. and Silva, V. H. S. and Cerdiera, A. and Wang, Bo and Wen, Jiwang and Zheng, Jia			Communications in Computer and Information Science	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
401	Scopus	Research on Assessment and Comparison of the Forest Open Government Data Quality Between China and the United States	Wang, Bo and Wen, Jiwang and Zheng, Jia			Communications in Computer and Information Science	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
402	IEEE	Risk based Payment Integrity Evaluation	Ekni, Tahr and LaKomski, Greg				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
403	IEEE	Role of Business Intelligence Systems in Croatian Higher Education Quality Assurance	Brečić, M. Cvitanović				2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 8, All Open Access, Gold Open Access, Bronze Open Access
404	Scopus	Technology against COVID-19: A blockchain-based framework for data quality	Ezzine, Imane and Benhima, Lala			Colloquium in Information Science and Technology	2020	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 7, All Open Access, Bronze Open Access
405	ACM	Towards a maturity model for corporate data quality management	H'YUjaya, K. M. and Omer, Martin and Otto, Boris				2009	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/1529282.1529334	Accepted	Sim	Finalizado	6	Não extralve	Article	8	Relevance to Data Quality or Data Governance	
406	IEEE	Star Schema Implementation For Monitoring in Data Quality Management Tool (A Case Study at PT. Telkom Indonesia)	Efendy, Mohammad Reza and Kusumasan, Tien Fabrianti and Anon, Fikri Muzakkar and Huting, Zhengfalsfo Evidence and Analysis of Quality Management to Improve Service				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Duplicated	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Duplicated Publication	
407	Scopus	The effects of demographic variables on Master of Science Quality Management to Improve Service	Huting, Zhengfalsfo Evidence and Analysis of Quality Management to Improve Service			2019 International Conference on Smart Automation	2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Duplicated	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Duplicated Publication	
408	IEEE	An Comparative Study of Open Education Data between China and UK	Miao, Zhenzhen and Zhai, Jun and Lin, Yan and Yuan, Changfeng				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
409	IEEE	A Survey on the Problems Affecting the Development of Open Government Data Initiatives	Roa, Henry N. and Loza-Aguirre, Edison and Flores, Pamela				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
410	IEEE	An Analysis of Students' Urban Mobility using Arequipa Smart Mobility Application	Suarez-Lopez, Ernesto and Bultron-Reveliz, Cortiya and Lavra-Ochoa, Yohana and Pariban, K. and Nataraj, R. V.				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
411	IEEE	An Efficient Architecture to Ensure Data Integrity in ERP Systems	Pariban, K. and Nataraj, R. V.				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
412	IEEE	An Empirical Framework for Day-Ahead Forecast of PV Output Power in Smart Grids	Raza, Muhammad Qasim and Mirulhaq, Nadeem and Li, Rongrong and Raza, Muhammad Qasim and Mirulhaq, Nadeem and Li, Rongrong			IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
413	IEEE	An Open Government Data Maturity Model - A Case Study in BPS-Statistics Indonesia	Rahmawati, Mithu and Kriyandani, Dewi and Rahmawati, Sinta Derovi				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
414	IEEE	Big Data Driven Smart Agriculture: Pathway for Sustainable Development	Min and Chantanthai, Bouasone and Hsuan, Mohd helal				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
415	IEEE	Big Data Impacts and Challenges: A Review	Al-Sai, Zaher Ali and Abdullah, Rosni and Hsuan, Mohd helal				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
416	IEEE	Calibration Improvements in S-NPP VIIRS DNB Sensor Data Record Using Version 2	Uprety, Sirsh and Cao, Changyong and Guo, Yalong and Shao, Xi and Wang, Yanyan and Wang, Yanyan			IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing	2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
417	IEEE	Compliance with Open Data Principles: A Longitudinal Content Analysis of the Saudi's Open Government Data Initiatives	Ghaurav, Mohammed A. and Aneame, Hashim H. and Hamed, Khalid M. and Aneame, Hashim H.				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.	https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428503	Rejected	Não			Anda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1
418	IEEE	Construction of Elevator Inspection Quality Evaluation System Based on Big Data	Zhang, Xupeng and Liang, Du				2019	Novel diseases such as COVID-19 present challenges for identifying and assessing the impact of public health interventions due to incomplete and inaccurate data. Many Governments look towards national statistical organizations (NSO) for high quality data with which to improve decision making processes. Digital data collection (DDC) offers NOAA in recent years, Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMS) have become widely used in hydrographic surveys and oceanographic studies, especially in coastal regions. NOAA's Background Public health services require valid, timely and complete health information for early detection of outbreaks.</										

Article Reference	Origin	Title	Author	Country	Continent	Journal	Year	Abstract	url	Status	Downloaded	Situação Leitura	Quality Checklist score	Quality Checklist Result	Document Type	# Pages	Selection Criteria	note
621	IEEE	Project management and data quality control	Tien, David				2010	The Building Sustainability Index (BASIX) is a government initiative at the New South Wales (NSW) Australia to assess the potential performance of new homes against a range of Data quality evaluation of coal and gas outburst		Duplicated	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Duplicated Publication	
622	Scopus	Study on data quality evaluation of coal and gas outburst	Dong, Lihong and Hou, Yunbing			Proceedings of the International Conference on	2010	The effect of data quality on data mining - Improving prediction accuracy by generic data	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2010.5584277	Duplicated	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Duplicated Publication	Cited by: 0
623	IEEE	Assessment of reanalysis datasets using AIRS and IASI hyperspectral radiances	Wang, Likun and Goldberg, Mitch and Liu, Xingpin and Zhou, Liyang				2010	Assessment of reanalysis datasets using AIRS and IASI hyperspectral radiances		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
624	Scopus	Data quality and the detection of woody vegetation: Implications for environmental and Live Geography - Interoperable Geo-Sensor Webs Enabling Portability in Monitoring Applications	Famer, Elizabeth and Reinke, Karin J. and Lechner, Alex M. and Jones, Resch, Bernd and Mittlbach, Manfred			Accuracy 2010 - Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on	2010	This paper presents preliminary work into the data quality of a series of woody vegetation preference maps of differing spatial resolutions. The correspondence between two different maps in the last decade, rapidly declining sensor costs triggered intense research in sensor technologies and vice versa. The fact led to the development of a collaboration whenever multiple public organizations engage in information sharing and interoperable initiatives. However, few analyses exist on how Retracted.	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/AC2010.5584277	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Focus on Non-related technical aspect	Cited by: 0
625	IEEE	Multinational E-Government Collaboration, Information Sharing, and Interoperability: An Notice of Retraction: Research on Surveillance and Evaluation in Acceptance Stage of E-	Navarrete, Celene and Gil-Garcia, J. Ramon and Mellouli, Seli and				2010	Notice of Retraction: Research on Surveillance and Evaluation in Acceptance Stage of E-		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
626	IEEE	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst	Liu, Hongzhi and Yang, Rongyan and Li, Haoheng and Wan, Yueliang				2010	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
627	IEEE	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst	Quirchmayr, Gerald and Wills, Christopher C.				2010	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
628	IEEE	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst	Lihong, Dong and Yunbing, Hou				2010	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
629	IEEE	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst	Lihong, Dong and Yunbing, Hou				2010	Some Thoughts on the Legal Background of the Continuously Increasing Privacy Risk in Information Systems and their Role in Privacy in Study on Data Quality Evaluation of Coal and Gas Outburst		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
630	IEEE	The Data Management of E-government System in the Deepening Application Phase	Shaoyun, Guan and Xueina, Han and Junling, Li and Yongxin, Ou and Jun, Wang				2010	The Data Management of E-government System in the Deepening Application Phase		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
631	IEEE	The design and realization of GIS-based management information system for investment	Tian Guozhang and Li Bo				2010	The design and realization of GIS-based management information system for investment		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
632	Scopus	The effect of data quality on data mining - Improving prediction accuracy by generic data	Stang, Jergen and Hartvigsen, Tore and Retlan, Joachim			Proceedings of the 2010 International Conference on	2010	The effect of data quality on data mining - Improving prediction accuracy by generic data	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2010.5584277	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Focus on Non-related technical aspect	
633	IEEE	Trusted data in IBM's MDM: Accuracy dimension	Pawluk, Przemyslaw				2010	Trusted data in IBM's MDM: Accuracy dimension		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
634	IEEE	Understanding quality in data from hospital diagnosis and procedures: A statistical	Sato, Diogo and Freitas, Alberto				2010	Understanding quality in data from hospital diagnosis and procedures: A statistical		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
635	Scopus	Use of Medicare and DOD data for improving VA race data quality	Stroupe, Kevin T. and Tarlov, Elizabeth and Zhang, Qiyang and Brunner, Christopher and Peyrot, Thibaut			Journal of Rehabilitation Research and Development	2010	Use of Medicare and DOD data for improving VA race data quality	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1177/1545868910377176	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Article		Focus on Non-related technical aspect	Cited by: 46; All Open Access, Bronze Open
636	ACM	Visual metrics for the evaluation of sensor data quality in outdoor perception	Brunner, Christopher and Peyrot, Thibaut				2010	Visual metrics for the evaluation of sensor data quality in outdoor perception	https://doi.org/10.1145/1737716.1737758	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Irrelevant Research Focus			
637	Scopus	Data quality for decision support - The indian banking scenario	Dwivedi, Hemalatha and Vaidya, Aka			Data Quality and High-Dimensional Data Analysis - Proceedings of the PADEXA	2009	Data quality for decision support - The indian banking scenario	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/PADEXA.2009.5292911	Accepted	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Context in the Public Sector	Cited by: 2
638	IEEE	Building an Open Lab on Information Quality for future computer education	Ying Su and Jie Peng and Al-Hakim, Latif				2009	Building an Open Lab on Information Quality for future computer education		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
639	IEEE	Duplicate Record Detection for Database Cleansing	Rehman, Mariam and Eschkaik, Veerachan				2009	Duplicate Record Detection for Database Cleansing		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
640	IEEE	Evaluation of 3D Visualization in the Virtual Environmental Planning Systems Project	Counsel, John and Richman, Andrew and Holding, Alan				2009	Evaluation of 3D Visualization in the Virtual Environmental Planning Systems Project		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
641	IEEE	Improving data quality with dynamic forms	Chen, Kuang and Chen, Harr and Conway, Neil and Dahan, Heather				2009	Improving data quality with dynamic forms		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
642	IEEE	NOAA's Physical Oceanographic Real-Time Systems (PORTS®)	Wright, Darren and Bassett, Robert				2009	NOAA's Physical Oceanographic Real-Time Systems (PORTS®)		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
643	IEEE	Noise mapping in urban environments: Application at Suez city center	Hossain Eldien, Hany				2009	Noise mapping in urban environments: Application at Suez city center		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
644	IEEE	The Problems Paid Attention to the Development of Urban Agglomeration GIS in China	Chen, Weigong and Chen, Weibao				2009	The Problems Paid Attention to the Development of Urban Agglomeration GIS in China		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
645	IEEE	The TAO shipboard CTD program under the National Data Buoy Center	Boyd, Janice D. and Croul, Richard L. and LeBlanc, Lex				2009	The TAO shipboard CTD program under the National Data Buoy Center		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
646	Scopus	Correcting the record on the data quality act [4]	Kelly, William G.			Science	2008	Correcting the record on the data quality act [4]	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1154277	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Letter		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 0
647	IEEE	Geographic Information Science: A Step Toward Geo-governance Solutions	Scarpitta, E. and Cardinali, S. and Scopelliti, A. and Valpiera, E.				2008	Geographic Information Science: A Step Toward Geo-governance Solutions		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
648	IEEE	IEEE Health Informatics-POC medical device communication Part 00101: Guide-Guidelines for Semi-automatic Codification of Economical Activities with Support Vector Machines	Correa, Fabiano Rogério and Okamoto Jr., Jun			IEEE Std 11073-00101-2008	2008	IEEE Health Informatics-POC medical device communication Part 00101: Guide-Guidelines for Semi-automatic Codification of Economical Activities with Support Vector Machines		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
649	IEEE	The correct attribution of codes to economical activities is of utmost importance for fiscal and administrative purposes. In a joint effort involving federal, state and city business regulating	Seelig, Frederick W.				2007	The correct attribution of codes to economical activities is of utmost importance for fiscal and administrative purposes. In a joint effort involving federal, state and city business regulating		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
650	IEEE	A Description of the August 2006 XG Demonstrations at Fort A.P. Hill	Seelig, Frederick W.				2007	A Description of the August 2006 XG Demonstrations at Fort A.P. Hill		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
651	Scopus	A systematic approach to ensure data quality within emerging systems	Guehl, Casey			Proceedings of the 2007 International Conference on	2007	A systematic approach to ensure data quality within emerging systems	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE.2007.4292911	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 0
652	Scopus	Data quality control in eco-environmental monitoring	Lu, Chunyan and Wang, Jing			Proceedings of SPIE - The International Society for	2007	Data quality control in eco-environmental monitoring	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1117/12.682277	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 0
653	IEEE	Enhanced e-Services through Partnerships-Increasing the Value of Public Infrastructure	Berlitz, Lasse				2007	Enhanced e-Services through Partnerships-Increasing the Value of Public Infrastructure		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
654	IEEE	SeaDataNet: Development of a Pan-European Infrastructure for Ocean and Marine Data	Mallard, Catherine and Lowry, Roy and Maudire, G. and Schaap, Dick and				2007	SeaDataNet: Development of a Pan-European Infrastructure for Ocean and Marine Data		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
655	Scopus	The tobacco industry and the data quality act [4]	Schick, Suzanne Franine and Berio, Lisa Anne and Cook, Daniel M.			Science	2007	The tobacco industry and the data quality act [4]	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1154277	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Letter		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 2
656	Scopus	An algebraic approach to data quality metrics for entity resolution over large datasets	Talbot, John and Wang, Richard and Hees, Kimberly and Kuo, Emily			Information Quality Management: Theory and	2006	An algebraic approach to data quality metrics for entity resolution over large datasets	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/IQM.2006.2622911	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Book Chapter		Focus on Non-related technical aspect	Cited by: 11
657	Scopus	Assuring data quality for ERP implementation: Part 2-comprehending the evolving picture	Alken, Peter and Metz, Chris and Berta, Anthony and Finkiel, Bill and			Proceedings of the 2006 International Conference on	2006	Assuring data quality for ERP implementation: Part 2-comprehending the evolving picture	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT.2006.2622911	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 0
658	IEEE	Buyer and Radar Observation Network around Taiwan	Kao, Chia-Chuen and Jao, Kuo-Ching and Doong, Dong-Jing and				2006	Buyer and Radar Observation Network around Taiwan		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
659	IEEE	Quality Control of Minerals Management Service - Oil Company ADCP Data at NDBC: A Successful	Croul, Richard L. and Conlee, Don T.				2006	Quality Control of Minerals Management Service - Oil Company ADCP Data at NDBC: A Successful		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
660	Scopus	Relationships among daily mean and maximum wind speeds, with application to data quality	Graybeal, Daniel Y.			International Journal of Climatology	2006	Relationships among daily mean and maximum wind speeds, with application to data quality	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1246	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 18
661	IEEE	Revolutionizing Rural Health Care Delivery Using Improved Health Information Systems - A	Quarshay, Z.B.				2006	Revolutionizing Rural Health Care Delivery Using Improved Health Information Systems - A		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
662	IEEE	Why CRM Efforts Fail? A Study of the Impact of Data Quality and Data Integration	Missi, F. and Alshawi, S. and Fitzgerald, G.				2005	Why CRM Efforts Fail? A Study of the Impact of Data Quality and Data Integration		Rejected	Sim	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
663	ACM	Data confidentiality, data quality and data integration for federal databases	Karr, Alan F.				2005	Data confidentiality, data quality and data integration for federal databases		Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
664	Scopus	Development of a database of critically evaluated flavonoid data: Application of USDA's data quality	Holden, Joanne M. and Bhagwat, Sreema A. and Hayowitz, David E.			Journal of Food Composition and Analysis	2005	Development of a database of critically evaluated flavonoid data: Application of USDA's data quality	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2005.06.001	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Article		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 62
665	Scopus	Salt sellers challenge US health agency using data-quality act	Wadman, Meredith			Nature	2005	Salt sellers challenge US health agency using data-quality act	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1038/435277a	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Note		Irrelevant Research Focus	Cited by: 1; All Open Access, Bronze Open
666	Scopus	Using automation and remote operation of monitoring stations to improve efficiency and data	Craig, Joel			Symposium on Air Quality Measurement Methods and	2005	Using automation and remote operation of monitoring stations to improve efficiency and data	https://www.scopus.com/recordurl.uri?https://doi.org/10.1117/12.682277	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Conference Paper		Irrelevant Research Focus	
667	ACM	Data confidentiality, data quality and data integration for federal databases	Karr, Alan F.				2004	Data confidentiality, data quality and data integration for federal databases		Duplicated	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado				
668	ACM	A general framework for query answering in data quality-based Cooperative Information Systems					2004	A general framework for query answering in data quality-based Cooperative Information Systems	https://doi.org/10.1145/1012453.1012461	Rejected	Não	Ainda não avaliado		Ainda não avaliado	Irrelevant Research Focus			

